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Do we really know by how much ellipsoidal shapes enhance the extinction of solar radiation by dust?

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Key Points:

- We combine a recent compilation of dust shape observations with scattering properties of ellipsoidal particles.
- Ellipsoids increase the dust shortwave extinction by one-fifth compared to spheres, improving the model mass extinction efficiency.
- Computed ellipsoidal scattering properties cover only one-third of observed dust shapes, limiting an assessment of the shape effect.

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Abstract

The climate impact of dust is still uncertain, partially due to poorly constrained dust physical and optical properties. Natural dust particles are known to have highly irregular shapes, but many models assume spheres when calculating the direct radiative effect (DRE). While the superior performance of non-spherical shapes in remote sensing applications has been widely recognized, there has been no consensus about the importance of dust non-sphericity in climate models. We assess the extent of the shape effect upon the dust optical properties and DRE at shortwave wavelengths within the NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies ModelE2.1. We assume tri-axial ellipsoids as an approximation to natural dust shapes that is suitable for model applications, and combine a widely used database of ellipsoidal single-scattering properties with a recent shape distribution constructed from a comprehensive compilation of measurements. We find a shape-induced enhancement of global dust extinction of +20% ($\pm 1\%$), resulting in a global cooling increase of +24% ($\pm 3\%$) at the top of atmosphere and +12% ($\pm 2\%$) at the surface. The ellipsoidal shapes increase the total dust extinction per unit mass, improving our model representation of the dust optical depth compared to a semi-observational constraint and ground-based measurements. However, our analysis shows that the database of ellipsoidal scattering properties covers only one-third of the observed distribution of shapes. This represents a major uncertainty in evaluating the dust shape effect in model applications.

Plain Language Summary

In sparsely vegetated areas, the wind lifts soil into the atmosphere, carrying the smallest particles (called ‘dust aerosols’) for thousands of kilometers. Dust is the most abundant aerosol species and impacts climate: for example, by heating and cooling the atmosphere. Climate models are computer programs that simulate the complex interactions among different components of the Earth system. Here, we refine the interaction between dust aerosols and solar radiation as calculated by a climate model developed at the NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies. For simplicity, most models approximate dust as perfect spheres, even though particles are observed with highly irregular shapes. Here, we assume more generally that dust particles are ellipsoids described by three dimensions of different length. Ellipsoids are attractive because their optical properties have been calculated for a range of particle dimensions, and because observed dimensions were recently compiled from global dust measurements. We show that ellipsoidal shapes enhance the impact of dust upon solar radiation compared to spheres, strengthening its climate effects and improving our model performance compared to observations. However, we note that ellipsoidal optical properties are still unavailable for many observed particle shapes, which challenges our ability to assess the climate effect of dust.

1 Introduction

Mineral dust from wind erosion of arid and semi-arid soils makes the largest contribution to the global load of atmospheric aerosols (Textor et al., 2006) and impacts the climate through radiation (Miller et al., 2014; F. Li et al., 2004), cloud formation (Nenes et al., 2014; Atkinson et al., 2013; Kok et al., 2023) and the carbon cycle (Jickells et al., 2014; Mahowald et al., 2011). Despite considerable observational and modeling efforts in recent years, estimates of the dust direct radiative effect (DRE) are still uncertain, partly due to the limited observational constraints upon the particle size distribution (Kok et al., 2017; Adebisi & Kok, 2020; Adebisi et al., 2023), mineral composition (L. Li et al., 2021; Gonçalves Ageitos et al., 2023; Obiso et al., 2024) and shape (Yi et al., 2011; Huang et al., 2023). These physico-chemical properties directly affect the dust optical depth (DOD), single-scattering albedo (SSA) and asymmetry parameter, which in turn influence shortwave (SW) and longwave (LW) radiative fluxes and the dust DRE.

68 The most simple and widely used model for dust particle shape is a sphere, because
69 exact solutions of scattering calculations based upon Mie theory (Mishchenko et al., 2002)
70 have a negligible computational cost and no practical limitations regarding particle size
71 (compared to wavelength) or the complex refractive index (CRI). However, dust parti-
72 cles are known to have highly irregular non-spherical morphology (Kalashnikova & Soko-
73 lik, 2004; Huang et al., 2020). Quantifying the error arising from the spherical assump-
74 tion in climate and remote sensing applications has long been of interest to the dust mod-
75 eling community. Early studies (Mishchenko et al., 1995, 1997) demonstrated that ran-
76 domly oriented spheroids, where one dimension is different from the remaining two, rep-
77 resenting a first step toward complexity with respect to spheres, led to significant dif-
78 ferences in the phase function at backscattering angles. The better performance of non-
79 spherical particle models in remote sensing applications was confirmed by later studies
80 (e.g., Dubovik et al., 2006; Merikallio et al., 2011; Huang et al., 2023). However, neither
81 spheroids (Merikallio et al., 2011; Huang et al., 2023) nor ellipsoids (Huang et al., 2023),
82 the latter defined by three different dimensions, were able to reproduce the measured phase
83 function of dust particles other than a sample of pure Feldspar (Volten et al., 2001), a
84 common mineral component of dust. (Dubovik et al. (2006) also used the Feldspar sam-
85 ple to validate a spheroidal model compared to spheres.) Nonetheless, ellipsoids have been
86 shown to reproduce better than spheres and spheroids the polarization elements of the
87 scattering matrix, not only for the Feldspar sample from Volten et al. (2001) but also
88 for two other natural dust samples (Huang et al., 2023).

89 Contrasting results have been reported about the importance of dust non-sphericity
90 for optical properties integrated over all scattering angles, which are typically used for
91 representing the interaction of dust with radiative fluxes in climate models. Mishchenko
92 et al. (1997) calculated negligible differences (below 10 %) in optical cross sections of spheroids
93 compared to spheres, a result that was later confirmed by Räisänen et al. (2013). How-
94 ever, Kalashnikova and Sokolik (2004) reported that more irregular shapes, which bet-
95 ter mimic the complex and varying morphology of observed dust particles, have a sig-
96 nificantly higher scattering efficiency compared to both volume-equivalent spheres and
97 spheroids. The database of single-scattering optical properties of tri-axial ellipsoids by
98 Meng et al. (2010a) allowed a higher degree of shape complexity that could be applied
99 to dust models (e.g., Colarco et al., 2014; Hoshyaripour et al., 2019; Klose et al., 2021).
100 While some modeling studies reported that ellipsoids have a critical impact upon dust
101 optical properties (Kok et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2023) and radiative fluxes (Yi et al.,
102 2011), other studies argued that non-spherical shapes (including ellipsoids) are unim-
103 portant to dust–climate interactions (Colarco et al., 2014) as well as the resemblance be-
104 tween modeled and observed DOD (Hoshyaripour et al., 2019) compared to other influ-
105 encing factors such as the dust CRI, emission flux and size distribution.

106 A key challenge to assessing the effect of particle shape upon the dust DRE is an
107 accurate characterization of the range and abundance of observed shapes. Ellipsoidal rep-
108 resentations typically assign independent particle dimensions along three perpendicu-
109 lar axes, defining the longest as the ‘length’, the shortest as the ‘height’ and the inter-
110 mediary as the ‘width’ (e.g., Huang et al., 2023). Kok et al. (2017) assumed a log-normally
111 distributed length-to-width ratio along with a constant height-to-length ratio. More re-
112 cently, Huang et al. (2020) compiled shape measurements of hundreds of thousands of
113 dust particles collected worldwide and summarized these measurements by fitting log-
114 normal distributions to both the length-to-width and height-to-width ratios (or ‘axis ra-
115 tios’).

116 In this work, we assess the impact of particle shape upon the dust DRE within the
117 NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies (GISS) ModelE2.1 (Section 2.1). We rep-
118 resent dust as a collection of ellipsoids using the independent distributions of axis ratios
119 from observations compiled by Huang et al. (2020). Similar to Huang et al. (2023), we
120 combine these distributions with the single-scattering properties provided by Meng et

al. (2010a) to calculate optical properties of ellipsoidal dust for the SW spectral bands of the model (Section 2.3). We compare the ellipsoidal model to a control case that assumes spheres (Section 2.2), analyzing the shape effect upon dust single-particle (Section 3.1) and global mean optical properties (3.2). We then assess the impact of ellipsoids upon the dust SW DRE accounting for the shape–radiation feedback upon the emitted dust mass (Section 3.3). We evaluate our results against semi-observational constraints upon the global annual mean DOD (Ridley et al., 2016) and mass load (Adebisi & Kok, 2020) (Section 3.2). These constraints are referred to as ‘semi-observational’ or ‘semi-empirical’ throughout the paper because they are based upon direct measurements along with model estimates of quantities where observations are lacking (Ridley et al., 2016; Kok et al., 2017). We also evaluate our model DOD with observations from the AEROSOL ROBOTIC NETWORK (AERONET; Holben et al., 1998) (Section 3.4) and the Multi-Angle Imaging Spectroradiometer (MISR; Garay et al., 2020) (Section 3.5). In Section 4, we discuss remaining uncertainties while our conclusions are presented in Section 5, where we appeal for a database of ellipsoidal scattering properties over a more extensive range of axis ratios that corresponds to the observed distribution of dust particle shapes.

2 Methods

2.1 Dust model

ModelE is the NASA GISS coupled atmosphere-ocean Earth system model (Schmidt et al., 2014; Kelley et al., 2020). The atmosphere component of ModelE2.1, the first GISS contribution to the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) (Kelley et al., 2020; Miller et al., 2021; Nazarenko et al., 2022), has horizontal resolution of 2.0° latitude by 2.5° longitude, and 40 vertical layers extending to the stratopause near 0.1 hPa. Within the troposphere, vertical resolution ranges from 20 hPa at the surface and tropical tropopause (near 150 hPa) to 50 hPa in the mid-troposphere (Schmidt et al., 2014). The One-Moment Aerosol (OMA) mass-based transport scheme (Bauer et al., 2020) simulates several externally mixed aerosol species, including mineral dust that can be configured either as a compositionally uniform species (Miller et al., 2006) (optionally with acidic coatings from heterogeneous uptake; Bauer & Koch, 2005) or as a mixture of minerals derived from the soil composition of dust sources (Perlwitz et al., 2015; Pérez García-Pando et al., 2016; Obiso et al., 2024). We implement the ellipsoidal shape only for compositionally homogeneous dust particles within an upgraded version of ModelE2.1 that, in addition to minor bug fixes, contains the updated scheme for coupling dust to radiation described in Appendix A.

Dust is emitted from easily erodible soils, here identified as sparsely vegetated topographic depressions (Ginoux et al., 2001), when the surface wind speed exceeds a threshold that varies with local soil moisture (Miller et al., 2006). The emitted particle size distribution is constructed from measurements of soil texture (after disturbance by wet-sieving techniques) through Brittle Fragmentation Theory (BFT) (Kok, 2011), and extended to diameters beyond the range of validity of the latter (above $20 \mu\text{m}$) according to concentration measurements during a dust outbreak in Morocco (Kandler et al., 2009). This prescribed distribution, which is borrowed from the mineral version of the dust model in ModelE2.1 (Perlwitz et al., 2015), results in enhanced emission of coarse dust particles and thus in larger fractions of the coarse mass load compared to previous versions of ModelE along with most state-of-the-art climate models (Adebisi & Kok, 2020). Mineral dust is transported within five size bins ranging from 0.1 to $32 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, with clay-sized particles (whose diameters are less than $2 \mu\text{m}$) distributed into four sub-bins for radiative calculations (Table 1). Removal occurs through gravitational settling and (dry) turbulent deposition, as well as wet deposition processes including in-cloud removal through nucleation and below-cloud scavenging by impaction (Perlwitz et al., 2015).

Table 1. Bounding diameters (d_A , d_B) of the five transport bins (‘Clay’, ‘Silt-1’, ‘Silt-2’, ‘Silt-3’, ‘Silt-4’). To improve the representation of the dust–radiation interaction at solar wavelengths, the clay bin is split into four sub-bins, resulting in a total of eight size bins for radiative calculations. The transported clay mass is re-distributed according to constant weights based upon the emitted PSD (Perlwitz et al., 2015): 0.00430, 0.03225, 0.23742 and 0.72603 (from finest to largest sub-clay bins). The effective diameter of each bin (d_e) is the double of the projected-area-weighted mean radius (Hansen & Travis, 1974). The prescribed mass density of each bin (ρ) used for calculating the dust optical depth and settling speed is also reported. Despite our assumption of a particle refractive index that is independent of size, mass density is slightly different in clay and silt bins (Tegen & Fung, 1994).

Bin	(d_A, d_B) (μm)	d_e (μm)	ρ (g cm^{-3})
Clay	(0.10, 0.36)	0.177	2.500
	(0.36, 0.60)	0.460	2.500
	(0.60, 1.20)	0.832	2.500
	(1.20, 2.00)	1.532	2.500
Silt-1	(2.00, 4.00)	2.773	2.650
Silt-2	(4.00, 8.00)	5.546	2.650
Silt-3	(8.00, 16.00)	11.09	2.650
Silt-4	(16.00, 32.00)	22.18	2.650

171 In this work we run two global simulations with interactive dust, covering a 30-year
172 period after 1 year of spin-up. The two experiments only differ in the assumed dust par-
173 ticle shape, spheres (‘SPH’) versus tri-axial ellipsoids (‘ELL’), for calculating the opti-
174 cal properties of dust in the SW bands of ModelE2.1 (Section 2.2 and Section 2.3, re-
175 spectively). While randomly oriented ellipsoids have greater projected area and aerody-
176 namic drag that reduces their settling speed by 15% compared to spheres (Huang et al.,
177 2020; L. Li et al., 2022), in this work we neglect this effect to allow comparison to pre-
178 vious studies that included only the radiative effect of shape (e.g. Colarco et al., 2014).

179 The spatially invariant coefficient relating the emitted mass of dust to surface wind
180 speed is pre-calculated using ModelE2.1 with spherical particles to minimize the mean
181 error of the model DOD and surface concentrations compared to an array of observa-
182 tions (cf. Cakmur et al., 2006). In this work, we use the same coefficient relating emis-
183 sion to surface wind in both the shape experiments, which results in a global extinction
184 of 0.024 and 0.029 for the spherical and ellipsoidal models, respectively, as averages across
185 ultraviolet (UV) and visible (VIS) wavelengths. Both these model values are consistent
186 with the observationally constrained estimate of 0.03 ± 0.01 at $0.550 \mu\text{m}$ by Ridley et
187 al. (2016).

188 Despite the identical emission coefficient in the two experiments, global emission
189 differs due to a feedback of the dust DRE upon the surface wind. This radiation–emission
190 feedback is negative in ModelE and has been traced to a local interaction between dust
191 and the planetary boundary layer, where a reduction of radiation incident upon the sur-
192 face beneath the dust layer reduces the flux of sensible heat back into the atmosphere
193 (Miller, Perlwitz, & Tegen, 2004; Pérez et al., 2006). This flux drives mixing within the
194 boundary layer along with the mixing of fast air aloft down to the surface, so a reduc-
195 tion in the sensible heating of the atmosphere reduces the surface wind speed and dust
196 emission. (ModelE parameterizes wind gusts in terms of the sensible heat flux, Cakmur

et al., 2004, so the reduction in gustiness is another contribution to the negative feedback.) We speculate that the greater aerodynamic drag and slower settling speed of ellipsoidal particles, which we neglect, would amplify this negative feedback by increasing the particle lifetime and thus the reduction of incident radiation at the surface. Additionally, dust radiative heating can perturb the regional atmospheric circulation (Heinold et al., 2007; Ahn et al., 2007), which changes the surface wind in a complicated way, and whose analysis is beyond the scope of our study.

Ozone and aerosols other than dust are prescribed from simulations of the CMIP6 historical period (1850–2014) calculated with the OMA scheme (Bauer et al., 2020).

2.2 Optical properties of spherical dust

For spherical particles, the calculation of dust optical properties (i.e., extinction and scattering efficiencies along with the asymmetry parameter) is detailed in Appendix A. The optical properties are calculated by integration over the particle radius, within each size bin, of monodisperse Mie parameters that are functions of the spectrally varying particle CRI and the size parameter (Mishchenko et al., 2002), the latter defined as the ratio of the radius to the incident wavelength (Equation A1). Single-wavelength optical properties are then averaged over each of the six SW bands of ModelE2.1, using the solar flux measurements from Thekaekara (1974) as a weighting function.

The imaginary part of the refractive index (IRI) is prescribed by smoothly joining values retrieved by Sinyuk et al. (2003) at UV–VIS wavelengths with values measured by Volz (1973) at infrared (IR) wavelengths longer than $2.5\ \mu\text{m}$. The real part of the refractive index (RRI) is based upon values reported by Patterson et al. (1977) and Volz (1973). Our prescribed CRI values at UV–VIS wavelengths are reported in Table S1 in Supporting Information. While there is general consensus in the literature about the RRI at solar wavelengths, the IRI exhibits a wider range of estimates because it strongly depends upon the dust mineral composition (Di Biagio et al., 2019; Castellanos et al., 2024). Our choice of IRI at UV–VIS wavelengths, based upon Sinyuk et al. (2003), results in lower absorption compared to other widely used prescriptions (e.g., Patterson et al., 1977; Hess et al., 1998) and a smaller model bias with respect to AERONET SSA (Obiso et al., 2024). At IR wavelengths, the total extinction is augmented by 30% to approximate the effect of scattering that is not explicitly calculated (Schmidt et al., 2014).

2.3 Optical properties of ellipsoidal dust

We incorporate the non-spherical effect in the dust-radiation coupling of ModelE2.1 by replacing the set of monodisperse optical properties derived from Mie theory with a corresponding set of properties for tri-axial ellipsoids. Following Huang et al. (2023), we derive the latter from the database of Meng et al. (2010a) (MengDB hereafter), which provides single-scattering properties of randomly oriented non-spherical particles over a five-dimensional grid consisting of size parameter, RRI, IRI and two different aspect ratios defining the specific particle shape. Ellipsoidal calculations in MengDB were performed by combining scattering codes based upon the Amsterdam Discrete Dipole Approximation (ADDA; Yurkin & Hoekstra, 2011) and the modified Improved Geometric Optics Method (IGOM; Bi et al., 2009; Yang et al., 2007; Yang & Liou, 1996) to cover small-to-large size parameters. Our inputs to MengDB are the same CRI values used for spherical dust and the grid aspect ratios corresponding to pure ellipsoids.

Details of our ellipsoidal calculation are given in Appendix B; here we outline the main features of our method. In addition to particle size and the CRI, the monodisperse optical properties of ellipsoids depend upon their specific shape. We use slightly different shape descriptors from those used in MengDB. Following Huang et al. (2023), we refer to minor, intermediate and major axes of a tri-axial ellipsoid as the ‘height’, ‘width’

246 and ‘length’, respectively. We then use the length-to-width ratio (LWR) and height-to-
 247 width ratio (HWR) as shape descriptors. We characterize the ellipsoidal particle size us-
 248 ing a generalized size parameter (Equation B1), with the radius corresponding to a volume-
 249 equivalent sphere. The monodisperse optical properties for tri-axial ellipsoids at each volume-
 250 equivalent radius are averaged over all the different randomly oriented ellipsoids that have
 251 the same volume. Once the monodisperse single-wavelength ellipsoidal optical proper-
 252 ties are obtained at the prescribed CRI values, through bilinear interpolation, we inte-
 253 grate them within the bounds of the size bins. (Using the volume-equivalent radius en-
 254 sures that different ellipsoids with same mass are associated to the same size bin.). Size
 255 integration and the averaging over the six SW bands of ModelE2.1 follow the same pro-
 256 cedure used for spherical dust (Appendix A).

257 We weight the different ellipsoidal shapes based upon two empirical log-normal dis-
 258 tributions of the axis ratios, the HWR and the deviation of LWR from unity (Equation
 259 B10), derived by Huang et al. (2020) based upon dozens of shape measurement compi-
 260 lations. From their global compilation, Huang et al. (2020) derived the global medians
 261 (1.70 and 0.40 for LWR and HWR, respectively) and the standard deviations (0.70 and
 262 0.73 for LWR and HWR, respectively) of the two distributions. They reported modest
 263 regional variations of both distributions, with large uncertainty due to limited samples
 264 from some areas, along with a low sensitivity to the particle size.

265 Figure 1 plots the observed likelihood of each combination of axis ratios, given by
 266 the product of the distributions in Equation B10, along with the shape domain where
 267 single-scattering optical properties are available in MengDB (green region; Appendix B3),
 268 the additional domain covered by Huang et al. (2023) by extending the optical proper-
 269 ties of the most extreme available ellipsoids to those shapes not included in MengDB (red
 270 region), and the domain containing extreme shapes that are observed (e.g., Okada et al.,
 271 2001) but not included in MengDB nor considered in Huang et al. (2023) (orange region).
 272 (The yellow region in Figure 1 includes shapes that are in principle allowed but scarcely
 273 observed, whereas the gray regions are forbidden by definition.) After re-normalizing the
 274 joint probability density for axis ratios within the intervals (1, 3.(3)) for the LWR and
 275 (0, 1) for the HWR (green, red and orange regions), where most ellipsoids are expected
 276 based upon Huang et al. (2020), we calculate that ellipsoidal optical properties in MengDB
 277 are available for only 29 % of the observed particle shapes, thus excluding the majority
 278 of the expected shapes. Even the mode of the joint probability density, representing the
 279 most likely ellipsoidal shape, is outside the domain covered by MengDB. The size of the
 280 dots in Figure 1 shows the magnitude of the extinction efficiency at $0.550 \mu\text{m}$. As shown
 281 in previous studies, (e.g., Kok et al., 2017), extinction is larger for ellipsoidal shapes com-
 282 pared to spheres. However, whether this increase persists for ~ 70 % of expected dust
 283 particle shapes that lie outside of the MengDB domain is unknown. In this study, we
 284 calculate the effect of dust non-sphericity only for shapes whose optical properties are
 285 available from MengDB (i.e., the green region), but this leaves the shape effect unresolved
 286 for over two-thirds of observed particles. This represents a major uncertainty in assess-
 287 ing the radiative impact of the dust non-sphericity, not only in our work but also in pre-
 288 vious studies that represented dust as ellipsoids.

289 2.4 AERONET dust measurements

290 To evaluate the performance of our two shape models (spheres and ellipsoids), we
 291 use DOD observations from AERONET (Version 3; Sinyuk et al., 2020). In order to iden-
 292 tify AERONET scenes where dust dominates the aerosol extinction and contributions
 293 by non-dust species are negligible, we apply strict multiple conditions to AERONET hourly
 294 inversion data (Obiso et al., 2024; Gonçalves Ageitos et al., 2023) matching all the qual-
 295 ity assurance criteria of the Level 2.0 inversion product (Holben et al., 2006) except for
 296 the threshold of 0.4 for the aerosol optical depth (AOD) at $0.440 \mu\text{m}$ (J. Li et al., 2014).

Figure 1. Contour plot of the joint probability density of the ellipsoidal shapes, given by multiplying the two log-normals in Equation B10, as a function of the two axis ratios: length-to-width ratio (ϵ_l) and height-to-width ratio (ϵ_h). The joint probability density (contour lines) is re-normalized within the domain composed of green, red and orange regions, that correspond to observed shapes (Huang et al., 2020; Okada et al., 2001). The blue star marker in the orange region represents the mode of the joint probability density, that is the most likely ellipsoidal shape. The green region is sampled by the database of Meng et al. (2010) (MengDB). Green plus red regions cover the axis ratio intervals considered by Huang et al. (2023). Orange and yellow regions extend to $\epsilon_h < 0.3$ and $\epsilon_l > 3.(3)$, respectively. (Gray regions are not allowed by definition of the axis ratios.) The axis ratio pairs of ellipsoids actually included in MengDB are identified by dots in the green region, whose size increases as a function of the bulk extinction efficiency prescribed by MengDB. For this specific calculation, a wavelength of $0.550 \mu\text{m}$ and prescribed real and imaginary indices of 1.558 and 0.0014, respectively, are used (Table S1 in Supporting Information). Moreover, a gamma distribution with effective radius of $1.0 \mu\text{m}$ and effective variance of 0.1 is used for size integration. Sub-domains defined by $\epsilon_l = 1$ and $\epsilon_h = 1$ correspond to oblate and prolate spheroids, respectively, while the spherical case is the dot identified by $\epsilon_l = 1$ and $\epsilon_h = 1$.

297 As a first filtering condition, we require a fine-volume fraction below 0.10 to sep-
 298 arate dust from fine species. To filter out possible coarse sea salt and further reduce non-
 299 dust species, we also require an increasing SSA between 0.440 and 0.675 μm , which is
 300 a typical feature of dust retrievals (Dubovik et al., 2002). Our third condition is that the
 301 mean retrieved IRI at 0.675, 0.870 and 1.020 μm must be below 0.0042, which separates
 302 ‘pure’ dust from ‘pure’ biomass burning retrievals based upon strict criteria (Schuster
 303 et al., 2016). The dusty scenes we identify through these conditions substantially over-
 304 lap with those where SW absorption is attributed to hematite and goethite (Schuster
 305 et al., 2016), two iron-bearing minerals commonly found within dust particles whose abun-
 306 dance determines spatial variations in SW dust absorption (Formenti et al., 2008; Moosmüller
 307 et al., 2012; Di Biagio et al., 2019).

308 To form a monthly climatology, we apply this multiple filtering to data from 2000
 309 to 2020 and impose a minimum of 80 cumulative hourly measurements per calendar month,
 310 which results in 38 stations (Table S2 in Supporting Information). We calculate AERONET
 311 DOD within the UV–VIS band of ModelE2.1 (0.30–0.77 μm) by extending measurements
 312 at specific wavelengths through a cubic spline and applying the same averaging procedure
 313 used for model dust (Appendix A).

314 In AERONET, the aerosol inversion threshold of 0.4 for AOD at 0.440 μm is in-
 315 tended to ensure sufficient aerosol to achieve a small error of hourly SSA (~ 0.03 ; Dubovik
 316 et al., 2002; Sinyuk et al., 2020). While AOD is directly measured by AERONET Sun
 317 photometers, and thus not affected by the inversion error, we use SSA and other retrieved
 318 variables to identify dusty scenes. Thus, relaxing the threshold upon AOD at 0.440 μm
 319 implies that our identification admits some less precise aerosol inversions. We argue that
 320 this relaxation offers compensating benefits. First, unlike SSA, AOD is less sensitive to
 321 the presence of species other than dust, because variations in aerosol absorption do not
 322 greatly affect the total extinction. Therefore, the AOD error we introduce by mistak-
 323 enly allowing a fraction of non-dust scenes broadly arises from additional mass of these
 324 other species. Second, this error is smaller for our monthly averages, comprised of more
 325 than 80 hourly measurements, than individual scenes whose retrieval is vulnerable to non-
 326 dust species. Third, while we could compare to AERONET more precisely by exclud-
 327 ing model values below the threshold, our method allows us to evaluate, despite some
 328 imprecision, the full range of model DOD.

329 2.5 MISR aerosol product

330 As an independent evaluation of our shape models, we also compare the model DOD
 331 with retrievals from a recent MISR aerosol product (Garay et al., 2020). The MISR in-
 332 strument has been retrieving aerosol properties from the NASA Earth Observing Sys-
 333 tem (EOS) Terra satellite since early 2000. Its multi-angle imaging system is composed
 334 of nine cameras oriented along the direction of the satellite motion which make obser-
 335 vations in four spectral channels (0.446, 0.558, 0.672 and 0.867 μm). The Level 3 aerosol
 336 product includes globally gridded data with a $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ spatial resolution. Among other
 337 properties, the single-wavelength AOD is provided for different ensembles of particles:
 338 all, small, medium, large, spherical and non-spherical. To perform a meaningful model–
 339 MISR comparison, along with a complementary MISR–AERONET validation, we pro-
 340 cess the MISR data as follows: 1) we aggregate the MISR daily all-particle AOD into
 341 a monthly climatology (2003–2019); 2) we linearly interpolate the MISR gridded values
 342 at the AERONET stations selected through the dust filtering (Section 2.4), while mask-
 343 ing months not included in the AERONET sample; and 3) we average the single-wavelength
 344 AOD over the UV–VIS band of ModelE2.1, consistent with our procedure for AERONET
 345 retrievals. Applying the same spatio-temporal mask defined by the dust filtering in AERONET
 346 reduces the number of available MISR retrievals but ensures that the all-particle AOD
 347 is primarily determined by dust aerosols.

3 Results

3.1 Monodisperse optical properties

In Figure 2, we show monodisperse optical properties for spherical and ellipsoidal dust particles, corresponding to our prescribed CRI at $0.550\ \mu\text{m}$ (Table S1 in Supporting Information), as a function of the size parameter. (For ellipsoids, this is the volume-equivalent size parameter.) As explained in Appendix B1, there are alternative definitions of extinction efficiency of an ellipsoid (the same applies to all the optical efficiencies, also including scattering and absorption), which in general is the extinction cross section divided by a projected area of the particle. (In this work, with ‘projected area’ we implicitly refer to the orientation-averaged projected surface area of a convex particle.) This ambiguity derives from the different possible definitions of size for a non-spherical particle (Gasteiger & Wiegner, 2018). For example, Bi et al. (2009) divide the extinction cross section by the projected area of a surface-equivalent sphere, whereas Kok et al. (2017) normalizes by the projected area of a volume-equivalent sphere. In Figure 2, we compare both these definitions of ellipsoidal optical efficiencies to spherical optical efficiencies (SPH, red curves): the solid blue curves (ELL-V) refer to volume-equivalent efficiencies, whereas the dashed blue curves (ELL-A) refer to surface-equivalent efficiencies.

The ellipsoidal optical efficiencies are smooth compared to those of spheres, mainly because of the lower symmetry of ellipsoids which damps the secondary interference maxima and the ripples typical of scattering by spherical particles (Hansen & Travis, 1974). Part of the smoothness also arises from our averaging over different ellipsoidal shapes that share the same volume-equivalent size parameter. The extinction efficiency is generally larger for ellipsoids than for spheres (Figure 2a), mainly due to a higher scattering efficiency (Figure 2b). This result is consistent with previous works (e.g., Kok et al., 2017; Hoshyaripour et al., 2019; Huang et al., 2023). Also, the ellipsoidal volume-equivalent optical efficiencies (solid blue curves) are always larger than the surface-equivalent optical efficiencies (dashed blue curves): this is expected because the projected area is always smaller for a volume-equivalent sphere than for a surface-equivalent sphere (Gasteiger & Wiegner, 2018). In Appendix B1, we show that the two definitions of optical efficiencies are related by the ratio of the surface-equivalent to volume-equivalent projected areas (the former by definition equal to the actual projected area of the ellipsoid). We refer to this ratio as the ‘geometric ratio’ (Equation B7) and calculate a value of ~ 1.12 as its mean across all ellipsoids in MengDB weighted by the observed distributions of axis ratios from Huang et al. (2020) (Appendix B3). This ratio accounts for the difference between the solid and dashed blue curves in Figures 2a–2c.

The geometric ratio enhances all the optical efficiencies by the same factor and therefore it does not affect the SSA (defined as the ratio of scattering to extinction efficiencies; Hansen & Travis, 1974), i.e. the solid and dashed blue curves in Figure 2d perfectly overlap. However, even without the effect of the geometric factor, the SSA is slightly higher for ellipsoids than for spheres. This demonstrates that the optical effect of non-sphericity primarily enhances the scattering efficiency of the particles: the surface-equivalent absorption efficiency (dashed blue curve in Figure 2c) is actually very close to that of spheres.

3.2 Size-resolved model optical and mass properties

In Figure 3, we show size-resolved, global annual mean DOD and SSA in the UV–VIS band along with the global annual emission rate and mean mass load of modeled dust for both the spherical (SPH) and ellipsoidal (ELL) experiments.

Consistent with our analysis of monodisperse optical properties (Section 3.1), we see a significantly enhanced DOD (Figure 3a) in the ELL experiment compared to the SPH experiment. The bulk DOD increases from 0.024 to 0.029, that is by +20% ($\pm 1\%$):

Figure 2. Monodisperse a) extinction (Q_e), b) scattering (Q_s) and c) absorption (Q_a) efficiencies, along with the d) single-scattering albedo (ω), of spheres (SPH) and tri-axial ellipsoids (ELL-V and ELL-A for volume-equivalent and surface-equivalent definitions, respectively), as a function of the size parameter (x). On the top panels, the diameters (d) corresponding to the size parameters at a wavelength of $0.550 \mu\text{m}$ are reported. The optical properties are based upon real and imaginary indices of 1.558 and 0.0014, respectively, that are our prescribed values at $0.550 \mu\text{m}$ (Table S1 in Supporting Information).

Figure 3. Size-resolved global annual mean a) optical depth (τ) and b) single-scattering albedo (ω), along with the global annual c) emission rate (E) and d) mean mass load (L) based upon a 30-year climatology of modeled dust from the spherical (SPH) and the ellipsoidal experiments with (ELL) and without (ELL-O) the shape–radiation feedback upon the emitted dust mass. The optical properties are averaged over the spectral band of ModelE2.1 covering ultraviolet and visible wavelengths (0.30–0.77 μm). In ModelE2.1, size bins cover diameters greater than 0.1 μm , with upper bounds at 2 (Clay), 4 (Silt-1), 8 (Silt-2), 16 (Silt-3), and 32 μm (Silt-4) (Table 1). In each panel, the total for each experiment and the PM₂₀ range (within parentheses) are reported.

398 the one-sigma error arising from standard error of the 30-year climatological means). The
 399 ellipsoidal DOD matches closely the semi-observational central estimate of 0.030 from
 400 Ridley et al. (2016), which is also used by Kok et al. (2017) and Adebisi and Kok (2020)
 401 for constraining global dust properties based upon observations and model calculations
 402 (with both studies using the ellipsoidal extinction efficiency from Meng et al., 2010a).
 403 Ito et al. (2021) calculated a nearly identical increase in DOD using ellipsoids, based upon
 404 MengDB and the shape distribution of Huang et al. (2020) with dust mass derived from
 405 a chemical transport model. Despite a different weighting of non-spherical shapes, also
 406 Colarco et al. (2014) found a similar increase of DOD due to ellipsoids from MengDB.

407 In Figure 3b, we see SSA increases that are modest for fine bins, whose SSA is already
 408 high for spheres, but become more important for coarse particles. The overall insensitiv-
 409 ity of global dust SSA to shape suggests that non-spherical effects might be mim-
 410 icked in a first approximation by applying pre-computed (and possibly size-specific) am-
 411 plification factors to the total extinction (e.g., L. Li et al., 2021). Nonetheless, this at-
 412 tractive model simplification neglects the shape effect upon SSA (and the asymmetry
 413 parameter), including near source regions where coarse dust is more abundant and the
 414 SSA sensitivity to shape is larger.

415 We also evaluate the shape impact upon the computed asymmetry parameter in
 416 the UV–VIS band (Figure S5d in Supporting Information), the third angle-integrated
 417 optical property typically used in models that give information about the dominant in-
 418 tegral direction of the scattered radiation. We find small variations of opposite sign across
 419 the size bins of ModelE2.1, positive in clay bins and negative in silt bins with a bulk re-
 420 lative variation of only 0.3%, in the ellipsoidal model (ELL) compared to the spherical
 421 case (SPH). While such variations may slightly affect the radiative fluxes at a regional
 422 scale, due to the dominant presence of either fine or coarse dust particles, globally the
 423 shape impact upon the asymmetry parameter appears of secondary importance compared
 424 to that on DOD and SSA.

425 Our PM_{20} mass load of ellipsoidal dust (34 Tg; Figure 3d) is slightly out of the range
 426 constrained by Kok et al. (2017) (14–33 Tg) but consistent with the subsequent range
 427 of Adebisi and Kok (2020) (18–44 Tg). This is likely due to our enhanced emission of
 428 coarse particles (Section 2.1). While in the fine range ($0.1 < d < 5 \mu\text{m}$), our ellipsoidal
 429 dust load of 14 Tg is very close to the estimates of both these studies (see Figure 3 of
 430 Adebisi & Kok, 2020), in the coarse range ($5 < d < 20 \mu\text{m}$) our value of 20 Tg is con-
 431 sistent with Adebisi and Kok (2020) (17 Tg) but is twice the value of Kok et al. (2017)
 432 (10 Tg).

433 Compared to spheres, the ellipsoidal shape slightly reduces both dust emission (-6%)
 434 and mass load (-7%) (Figures 3c and 3d, respectively). To interpret the results of the
 435 ellipsoidal model without the confounding effect of the shape–radiation feedback upon
 436 wind speed and dust emission, we re-calculate DOD and SSA offline by combining the
 437 column mass from the spherical experiment with ellipsoidal optical properties (ELL-O
 438 in Figures 3a and 3b). As a consequence, the DOD without the radiative feedback of shape
 439 is higher than the model DOD of ellipsoids ($+7\%$), exceeding the spherical DOD by $+28\%$.
 440 As mentioned in Section 2.1, the negative radiative feedback is likely related to weaker
 441 winds at the surface due to increased surface cooling caused by the larger DOD (Sec-
 442 tion 3.3). The analysis of the complicated adjustment of the global circulation to the dust
 443 DRE is beyond the scope of this study.

444 **3.3 Global distribution of model optical properties and direct radiative** 445 **effect**

446 In Figure 4, we show the radiative contrast between the ellipsoidal (ELL) and the
 447 spherical (SPH) experiments, using the globally distributed annual mean DOD and SSA
 448 in the UV–VIS band of the model, along with the annual mean broadband SW DRE at

449 the top of atmosphere (TOA) and the surface. Maps for the individual experiments are
 450 reported in Supporting Information, including optical properties (Figure S1) along with
 451 SW (Figure S2), LW (Figure S3) and the net (SW plus LW; Figure S4) DREs at TOA,
 452 in the atmosphere and at the surface.

453 In Figure 4a, we see the widespread regional increase of DOD due to the shape ef-
 454 fect, which is more significant over the main dust regions (e.g., the Saharan and Arabian
 455 deserts) where the spherical DOD is already high (Figure S1a in Supporting Informa-
 456 tion): DOD changes are mostly above 0.05 with peaks up to 0.17. In contrast, SSA in-
 457 creases are in general modest in transport regions (below 0.01) and larger over some source
 458 areas (up to 0.014), where coarse dust particles are more abundant (Figure 4b). This is
 459 consistent with the higher sensitivity of coarse particles to the shape effect (Figure 3b).
 460 Globally, the SSA increase of 0.01 is representative of high-DOD regions.

461 In Figure 4c, the combination of the higher DOD and SSA due to ellipsoids make
 462 the SW DRE at TOA more negative over all dust source and transport regions. Glob-
 463 ally, this leads to a cooling enhancement of +24% ($\pm 3\%$) with respect to the spherical
 464 model: from -0.303 to -0.375 W m^{-2} (Figures S2a and S2b in Supporting Information).
 465 According to a DRE efficiency of -12.6 W m^{-2} per unit DOD from the SPH experiment,
 466 we estimate a cooling enhancement at TOA of +28% without the radiative feedback of
 467 shape that reduces dust emission (Section 3.2). At the surface (Figure 4d), the higher
 468 SSA would in principle allow more forward-scattered radiation to reach the surface, but
 469 this effect is offset by the amplified extinction (Figure 4a) leading to a global increase
 470 of the cooling magnitude by +12% ($\pm 2\%$): from -1.22 to -1.36 W m^{-2} (Figures S2e
 471 and S2f in Supporting Information).

472 3.4 Comparison with AERONET dust optical depth

473 In Figure 5, we compare monthly DOD in the UV-VIS band from the spherical (SPH)
 474 and ellipsoidal experiments (ELL) with AERONET measured DOD at selected locations
 475 (Section 2.4). We use the Pearson correlation coefficient (r), the root mean square er-
 476 ror (e) and the mean bias (b) to evaluate the model performance against the observa-
 477 tions.

478 The SPH model (Figure 5a) qualitatively reproduces the spatio-temporal variabil-
 479 ity of the observed DOD ($r = 0.63$). However, the spherical model underestimates the
 480 observations in most stations and months, with a mean bias equal to -0.11 . This is con-
 481 sistent with our DOD from the SPH run underestimating the semi-observational con-
 482 straint of 0.030 by Ridley et al. (2016) (Section 3.2). In the ELL experiment (Figure 5b),
 483 the negative mean bias with respect to AERONET is reduced by 55% (-0.05), although
 484 the correlation does not improve (0.63). The reduced bias is consistent with the improved
 485 regression slope indicated by the green dashed line in Figure 5b that is closer to unity
 486 than for spherical particles (Figure 5a).

487 This result derives from the DOD amplification due to the shape effect, as can be
 488 seen by directly comparing the ellipsoidal and the spherical experiments in Figure 5c.
 489 As expected, the absolute contrast of DOD due to shape generally increases with DOD
 490 across different AERONET stations and calendar months, as it results from an ampli-
 491 fication of the extinction efficiency. This amplification is a function of size, ranging from
 492 18% to 33% across our size bins (Figure 3a). In Figure 5c, the ellipsoidal DOD slightly
 493 deviates from linearity with respect to the spherical DOD, because the (bulk) relative
 494 DOD contrast at each point depends upon the mass distribution across the bins calcu-
 495 lated by the model. In addition, the spatio-temporal distribution of dust mass is slightly
 496 different in the SPH and ELL experiments due to the shape-radiation feedback upon emis-
 497 sion.

Figure 4. Difference between the ellipsoidal (ELL) and spherical (SPH) experiments for annual mean a) optical depth (τ) and b) single-scattering albedo (ω), along with the annual mean all-sky shortwave direct radiative effect at the c) top of atmosphere ($R_{\text{toa}}^{\text{sw}}$) and d) surface ($R_{\text{sfc}}^{\text{sw}}$), based upon a 30-year climatology of modeled dust. The optical properties are averaged over the spectral band of ModelE2.1 covering ultraviolet and visible wavelengths (0.30–0.77 μm). The extremes of the color bars are set to the 1st and 99th percentiles of the mapped variables. Note that in panel b, the color scale is reversed: more intense blue indicates a higher single-scattering albedo (scattering relative to total extinction). Global means along with minimum and maximum (within parentheses) are also reported.

Figure 5. Monthly mean dust optical depth (τ) of 30-year modeled and AERONET (2000–2020) climatological dust, for all available calendar months at the selected stations (shown in panel d and listed in Table S2 in Supporting Information). AERONET measurements are separately compared to the spherical (SPH; a) and the ellipsoidal (ELL; b) experiments; the two model experiments are then directly compared (c). The dust optical depth (both from the model and AERONET) is averaged over the spectral band of ModelE2.1 covering ultraviolet and visible wavelengths (0.30–0.77 μm). For each panel, the number of monthly means (n), the Pearson correlation coefficient (r), the root mean square error (e) and the mean bias (b) are reported. The dashed green line in each panel is derived from linear regression and shows the overall resemblance.

498 The larger negative bias of the SPH experiment cannot be remedied simply by re-
 499 calibrating the global emission to increase its DOD, bringing it closer to the semi-observational
 500 constraint of 0.030 by Ridley et al. (2016). The necessary 20 % increase of DOD (Fig-
 501 ure 3a) would require a proportional increase of the PM₂₀ global load of spherical dust
 502 to $\sim 44 Tg$ (Figure 3d), far outside the semi-empirical range constrained by Kok et al.
 503 (2017) and at the highest end of the range proposed by Adebisi and Kok (2020) (Sec-
 504 tion 3.2). In contrast, the ELL experiment has a larger ratio of extinction to mass load
 505 (the mass extinction efficiency) that allows a better agreement with both observed op-
 506 tical and mass constraints (Ridley et al., 2016; Kok et al., 2017; Adebisi & Kok, 2020).

507 Discrepancies between model and observed DOD at specific locations and calen-
 508 dar months may be much larger than shape-induced changes to DOD: contrast the points
 509 corresponding to the largest errors in each individual experiment (Figures 5a and 5b)
 510 to the differences between the two shape models in Figure 5c. This confirms that an in-
 511 accurate representation of dust processes other than radiation remains a major source
 512 of uncertainty in correctly simulating the spatio-temporal distribution of the observed
 513 DOD (Hoshyaripour et al., 2019).

514 3.5 Comparison with MISR aerosol optical depth

515 In Figure 6, we compare model DOD from both our shape experiments with AOD
 516 retrieved by MISR. As reported in Section 2.5, we post-process MISR retrievals to ob-
 517 tain climatological monthly means of AOD in the UV–VIS band of ModelE2.1 at the same
 518 stations and months selected through the filtering of AERONET retrievals to identify
 519 dusty scenes (Section 2.4). MISR retrievals of AOD are highly correlated with AERONET
 520 (0.85), although for the dusty scenes that we select, MISR underestimates AERONET
 521 AOD with an average low bias of -0.07 (Figure 6c). Consistent with this underestimate,
 522 the spherical model (SPH; Figure 6a) achieves a smaller negative bias with respect to
 523 MISR (-0.04 versus -0.11 compared to AERONET). Similar to the comparison with
 524 AERONET, the ellipsoidal model (Figure 6b) further reduces the bias magnitude ($+0.02$),
 525 although the root-mean-square error increases slightly. Both models exhibit a higher cor-
 526 relation with MISR (0.79) than with AERONET (0.63), a contrast that is statistically
 527 distinct from zero. (The two-sided 95 % confidence range for both models with respect
 528 to AERONET is 0.53–0.71, given 180 independent monthly means that comprise the cor-
 529 relation, compared to 0.73–0.84 with respect to MISR.) This independent evaluation of
 530 our shape models affirms that the ellipsoidal shape improves the evaluation of the model
 531 DOD without the need for a higher dust mass that, as discussed in Section 3.2, would
 532 reduce our agreement with a semi-empirical constraint (Adebisi & Kok, 2020).

533 4 Uncertainties

534 Our experimental design and analysis are intended to assess the effect of non-spherical
 535 particle shapes upon dust optical properties for practical climate applications like cal-
 536 culating the dust DRE. This motivates our adoption of the tri-axial ellipsoid as an ap-
 537 proximation to natural dust particle shapes. While ellipsoids do not fully represent the
 538 complex morphology of real dust particles (Merikallio et al., 2011; Kalashnikova & Soko-
 539 lik, 2004), their higher degree of complexity compared to spheres allows a more accu-
 540 rate shape representation (Bi et al., 2009) along with a more significant effect, compared
 541 to spheroids (Mishchenko et al., 1997), upon model optical properties that are integrated
 542 over the scattering angle (Huang et al., 2023). Moreover, ellipsoids are an attractive rep-
 543 resentation because of a recent compilation of globally distributed measurements of par-
 544 ticle shape that have been fitted to ellipsoidal shape descriptors (Huang et al., 2020), whereas,
 545 to the best of our knowledge, global observations of more complex shape descriptors are
 546 not currently available. Saito et al. (2021) developed a new optical database providing
 547 ensemble optical properties of mixed irregular hexahedrons, mainly designed for improv-

Figure 6. Monthly mean optical depth (τ) of 30-year modeled and MISR (2003–2019) climatological dust, for all available calendar months at the selected stations from AERONET (shown in panel d and listed in Table S2 in Supporting Information). MISR retrievals are separately compared to the spherical (SPH; a) and the ellipsoidal (ELL; b) experiments; a complementary validation of MISR data against AERONET measurements is also presented (c). The dust optical depth (both from the model and MISR) is averaged over the spectral band of ModelE2.1 covering ultraviolet and visible wavelengths (0.30–0.77 μm). For each panel, the number of monthly means (n), the Pearson correlation coefficient (r), the root mean square error (e) and the mean bias (b) are reported. The dashed blue line in each panel is derived from linear regression and shows the overall resemblance.

548 ing the retrieval of aerosol properties in remote sensing applications. However, a robust
 549 characterization of the global distribution of hexahedral ensembles would be required to
 550 properly calculate the effect of non-sphericity upon dust optical properties and the global
 551 dust DRE.

552 All these considerations suggest that, while the ellipsoidal model is an improvable
 553 representation of dust shape, it currently appears to be the most practical candidate for
 554 our application to calculating the dust DRE. One limitation of uniformly applying a sin-
 555 gle shape model at all geographical locations is that variations of dust particle shape dur-
 556 ing transport are neglected. For example, more spherical shapes with less aerodynamic
 557 drag may be preferentially removed by gravitational settling (Huang et al., 2020). In ad-
 558 dition, coatings of hydrophilic aerosols like sulfate and nitrate produced by heterogeneous
 559 chemical reactions at the surface of dust particles (e.g., Bauer & Koch, 2005) enhance
 560 water up-take, leading to more spherical particles as a result of surface tension within
 561 the coating. The complexity required to represent regionally varying fractions of spher-
 562 ical and ellipsoidal particles is not currently available in ModelE2.1, which contributes
 563 uncertainty to the regional characterization of dust optical properties and the DRE.

564 Several studies have used the ellipsoidal shape model to represent dust non-sphericity
 565 in its interaction with radiation, making different assumptions about the shape of ob-
 566 served dust particles that is equivalent to applying different weighting methods for av-
 567 eraging the ellipsoidal shapes available in MengDB. Some studies (e.g., Yi et al., 2011;
 568 Colarco et al., 2014) calculated the ellipsoidal weights by matching the shape-averaged
 569 phase function to that of a Feldspar sample measured by Volten et al. (2001). In con-
 570 trast, Hoshyaripour et al. (2019) equally weighted the different ellipsoids. Other stud-
 571 ies (e.g., Kok et al., 2017) used an empirical distribution for the LWR, but only a sin-
 572 gle fixed value for the HWR. Dust extinction is highly sensitive to the specific shape de-
 573 scriptors (Hoshyaripour et al., 2019). Therefore, one source of diversity among litera-
 574 ture estimates of extinction is that different weighting methods lead to different impacts
 575 of the ellipsoidal shape upon DOD and the dust DRE.

576 Our method for weighting the scattering calculations available in MengDB is based
 577 upon the observationally constrained globally representative distributions of both LWR
 578 and HWR (Equation B10) determined by Huang et al. (2020). However, as discussed in
 579 Section 2.3, ellipsoidal solutions in MengDB are currently available for less than one-third
 580 of the observed particle shapes (the green region in Figure 1). To mitigate this restric-
 581 tion of the database, Huang et al. (2023) extrapolated the optical properties into the red
 582 region in Figure 1 using the MengDB solutions along the boundary with the green re-
 583 gion. This would further enhance the extinction of ellipsoids compared to spheres. How-
 584 ever, the shape-dependence of the optical efficiencies remains unknown in the extrap-
 585 olated red region, which accounts for roughly the same fraction of observed shapes as
 586 the region where solutions exist. Solutions are also absent for the remaining one-third
 587 of observed shapes (e.g., Okada et al., 2001) corresponding to the orange region that in-
 588 cludes the mode, or most commonly observed particle shape, of the joint probability den-
 589 sity.

590 As a sensitivity calculation that could motivate an expansion of MengDB, we con-
 591 sider the impact of an extended range of shapes, so that increasingly elongated or flat-
 592 tened particles are included. When allowing all the LWRs between 1 and 3.(3) for all
 593 the HWRs above 0.3 (the green plus red regions in Figure 1), the cumulative joint prob-
 594 ability of observed shapes that are included increases from 29 % (the integral over only
 595 the green region) to 61 %. Through extrapolation of solutions from the green region into
 596 the red region, we estimate the impact of the newly represented ellipsoids upon the DOD
 597 at $0.550 \mu\text{m}$ (see Supporting Information for more details). We find that each 10 % in-
 598 crease of the extinction efficiency of the ellipsoids in the red region results in a $\sim 7\%$
 599 enhancement of DOD at $0.550 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure S5 in Supporting Information: panels a, b and
 600 c). This sensitivity estimate is presented only for purposes of illustration, and cannot

601 be confirmed without expanding the fraction of observed particle shapes in the optical
 602 database. Decreasing the threshold for HWR to 0.1 would incorporate the mode of the
 603 joint probability density and raise the included fraction of observed shapes to 97%. Given
 604 the parsimony and broad global applicability of the shape distribution provided by Huang
 605 et al. (2020), we believe that the expansion of the MengDB tables could significantly re-
 606 duce the uncertainty of the DRE resulting from non-spherical dust particle shapes.

607 5 Conclusions

608 In this work, we assess the effect of particle non-sphericity upon dust optical prop-
 609 erties and the dust DRE within the NASA GISS ModelE2.1. We average the monodis-
 610 perse optical properties over different ellipsoidal particle shapes (Meng et al., 2010a) ac-
 611 cording to empirical distributions of the two axis ratios determined by Huang et al. (2020)
 612 based upon a vast compilation of available measurements of single dust particles.

613 Our results show that dust non-sphericity impacts radiation mainly through an ex-
 614 tinction enhancement. Despite a reduction of mass load (-7%) due to a shape-radiation
 615 feedback upon dust emission, non-sphericity amplifies the global annual mean DOD by
 616 $+20\%$ ($\pm 1\%$). This increase in the mass extinction efficiency of dust particles, in con-
 617 junction with strong emission at coarse sizes, significantly improves the agreement of our
 618 modeled dust with joint semi-observational constraints upon the global annual mean DOD
 619 (Ridley et al., 2016) and mass load (Adebisi & Kok, 2020). We highlight that our dust
 620 cycle is calibrated using independent worldwide observational constraints upon the spher-
 621 ical model version (Section 2.1), which makes the improved matching due to the enhanced
 622 extinction associated with ellipsoids more remarkable. Compared to spherical particles,
 623 the ellipsoidal shape also reduces the model low bias with respect to DOD measurements
 624 from AERONET (from -0.11 to -0.05) and MISR (from -0.04 to $+0.02$).

625 SSA of global dust shows less sensitivity to shape, although SSA increases are seen
 626 for coarse particles that are most abundant near source regions (Figure 3b). The greater
 627 aerodynamic drag of ellipsoidal particles would preferentially increase the lifetime of coarse
 628 particles (Huang et al., 2020). Therefore, including the effect of non-sphericity in the grav-
 629 itational settling could result in a more significant impact of the shape-induced SSA in-
 630 creases farther downwind from sources.

631 We calculate a cooling increase of $+24\%$ ($\pm 3\%$) at the TOA due to ellipsoids com-
 632 pared to spheres that is three times the estimate of Colarco et al. (2014) who found $+8\%$
 633 for ellipsoids within a coupled global circulation model. Our computed impact of ellip-
 634 soids upon the dust DRE at TOA is more in agreement with Yi et al. (2011) who cal-
 635 culated errors of the DRE at TOA up to 30% over dark sea surfaces, arising from spheres
 636 instead of ellipsoids within a stand-alone radiative transfer code. Differences between stud-
 637 ies can be attributed to contrasting assumptions about the abundance of specific par-
 638 ticle shapes, along with the combined effect of different dust size distributions, shape im-
 639 pacts upon SSA and asymmetry parameter, and environmental factors like clouds and
 640 surface albedo. We also highlight that the shape effect may be critical during strong dust
 641 events, because non-sphericity enhances the DOD in proportion to the column dust mass
 642 (Kalashnikova & Sokolik, 2004). This has implications for the regional dust DRE and
 643 its climate impact.

644 However, while ellipsoids represent a good compromise between the complexity of
 645 observed dust shapes and ease of representation within models, the currently available
 646 database of ellipsoidal optical properties (Meng et al., 2010a) covers only roughly one-
 647 third of the observed ellipsoidal shapes compiled by Huang et al. (2020). We calculate
 648 that 97% of the observed dust shapes could be represented (including the mode or most
 649 commonly observed shape of the joint probability density) if the database by Meng et
 650 al. (2010a) was extended to cover the axis ratio intervals of $1 < \epsilon_1 < 3.(3)$ and $0.1 <$

651 $\epsilon_h < 1$, although we acknowledge that optical calculations for such extreme ellipsoids
 652 could be challenging due to theoretical and computational limitations.

653 We conclude that the assessment of the importance of particle shape to the dust
 654 DRE and its climate impact remains incomplete due to the significant fraction of observed
 655 shapes whose scattering properties are unavailable. Paths forward could include expansion
 656 of the scattering database, or alternatively, new and globally representative comp-
 657 pilations of particle descriptors like the degree of sphericity that are inputs to more re-
 658 cent optical databases (e.g., Saito et al., 2021). Previous studies suggest that aspheric-
 659 ity significantly increases dust extinction (e.g. Kok et al., 2017). We encourage efforts
 660 to match optical calculations to global measurements of dust particles to resolve the mag-
 661 nitude of the shape effect.

662 **Appendix A Calculation of optical properties for spherical dust**

663 **A1 General definitions**

The extinction of electromagnetic radiation by a single spherical particle of radius r at a certain wavelength λ is given by its extinction cross section $C_e(m, x)$, where $m = n + ik$ is the CRI of the particle and x its size parameter

$$x = \frac{2\pi r}{\lambda}. \quad (\text{A1})$$

The extinction cross section is defined as the extinction efficiency of the particle $Q_e(m, x)$ multiplied by its projected area (or geometric cross section) $C_g(r) = \pi r^2$. For each model layer of thickness Δz , the spectral extinction optical depth τ_λ is given by multiplying the single-particle extinction cross section by the total number of particles in the layer per unit surface summed over all sizes:

$$\tau_\lambda = N\Delta z \int Q_e(m, x)\pi r^2 f_N(r) dr, \quad (\text{A2})$$

where $f_N(r)$ is the normalized number size distribution and N is the total number concentration (number of particles per unit volume), so that the product $f_N(r)Ndr$ gives the number concentration of particles with size between r and $r+dr$. Since ModelE2.1 calculates the mass of dust, we seek to express Equation A2 as a function of the mass concentration. To this end, we need the following relation of the number concentration to the mass concentration M :

$$N = \frac{M}{\int (4/3)\pi r^3 \rho f_N(r) dr}, \quad (\text{A3})$$

664 where ρ is the particle mass density, that we suppose to be constant with size, and $V(r) =$
 665 $(4/3)\pi r^3$ is the volume of a single particle. (Thus, the denominator of Equation A3 is
 666 the mean mass of a single particle.)

Another useful integral quantity is the number-weighted mean projected area, G , defined as

$$G = \int \pi r^2 f_N(r) dr. \quad (\text{A4})$$

Putting Equation A3 into Equation A2 and multiplying numerator and denominator of Equation A2 by the mean projected area in Equation A4 lead to

$$\tau_\lambda = \frac{\int Q_e(m, x)\pi r^2 f_N(r) dr}{\int \pi r^2 f_N(r) dr} \frac{\int \pi r^2 f_N(r) dr}{\int \frac{4}{3}\pi r^3 \rho f_N(r) dr} M\Delta z, \quad (\text{A5})$$

which can be rewritten as

$$\tau_\lambda = \frac{3 \langle Q_e \rangle}{4\rho r_e} M\Delta z, \quad (\text{A6})$$

where $\langle Q_e \rangle$ is the projected-area-weighted mean extinction efficiency:

$$\langle Q_e \rangle = \frac{\int Q_e(m, x) \pi r^2 f_N(r) dr}{\int \pi r^2 f_N(r) dr} \quad (\text{A7})$$

and r_e is the effective radius of the particle size distribution, defined as the projected-area-weighted mean radius (Hansen & Travis, 1974):

$$r_e = \frac{\int r \pi r^2 f_N(r) dr}{\int \pi r^2 f_N(r) dr}. \quad (\text{A8})$$

667 Equation A6 represents a direct relation between the dust extinction optical depth and
 668 the mass concentration in a given layer (Tegen & Lacis, 1996), and holds separately for
 669 extinction by scattering and absorption. The expressions for the projected area and the
 670 volume of a single particle used in the above equations apply only to spherical particles,
 671 whereas for ellipsoidal particles those definitions must be generalized (Appendix B).

672 **A2 Methods for size and spectral integration**

673 For spherical dust, we calculate monodisperse extinction and scattering efficiencies,
 674 along with the asymmetry parameter, using the Mie code by Mishchenko et al. (2002).
 675 The monodisperse optical properties depend only upon the CRI of the particles and their
 676 size parameter. We define a default set of 5000 size parameters: $0.02 \leq x \leq 1000$ with
 677 a constant logarithmic step. This range allows us to cover all our dust sizes ($0.1 \leq d \leq$
 678 $32 \mu\text{m}$) for all the solar wavelengths included in the SW bands of ModelE2.1 ($0.3 \leq \lambda \leq$
 679 $4 \mu\text{m}$). As detailed in Section 2.2, we prescribe the dust CRI by joining values from Sinyuk
 680 et al. (2003) (IRI) and Patterson et al. (1977) (RRI) at UV–VIS wavelengths with IR
 681 values from Volz (1973). In Table S1 in Supporting Information, we report the CRI at
 682 prescribed wavelengths covering the UV–VIS band of ModelE2.1 ($0.30\text{--}0.77 \mu\text{m}$).

683 We integrate the monodisperse optical properties over each size bin, including the
 684 four sub-clay ‘radiative’ bins (Table 1), selecting for each SW wavelength the correspond-
 685 ing CRI. For size integration, we assume a constant volume distribution with respect to
 686 the logarithm of particle radius within each bin. This assumption differs from that of
 687 the former dust optical calculation in ModelE that was based upon a standard gamma
 688 distribution with effective variance of 0.2 and prescribed effective radii corresponding to
 689 the transport bins (Tegen & Lacis, 1996). The gamma distribution is semi-infinite and
 690 includes contributions from particle sizes beyond the radial bounds of each size bin. (The
 691 use of a gamma distribution and its extension outside the nominal bin bounds was er-
 692 roneously described by Miller, Tegen, and Perlwitz (2004) and Miller et al. (2006).) In
 693 our updated approach, we derive the effective radius of each bin assuming the same sub-
 694 bin volume distribution used for integration of the optical properties, consistent with Miller
 695 et al. (2006).

696 As a final step, we average the size-integrated single-wavelength optical properties
 697 over the six SW bands of ModelE2.1, whose bounds are: 0.30, 0.77, 0.86, 1.25, 1.50, 2.20,
 698 $4.00 \mu\text{m}$. To properly calculate the radiative effect of dust across each solar band, we weight
 699 the single-wavelength properties by solar spectral irradiance measured near the tropopause
 700 and compiled by Thekaekara (1974), after mapping them onto a 10 nm-resolution wave-
 701 length grid through spline interpolation.

702 **Appendix B Calculation of optical properties for ellipsoidal dust**

703 **B1 Extension of general definitions**

In the OMA aerosol scheme of ModelE2.1, aerosol mass is transported within discrete bins, whose bounds are defined by the particle size. For spheres, the size corresponds to the particle radius (or diameter). For ellipsoids, that are generally defined by three

different axes, the definition of the particle size is not unique. We choose to define the size of an ellipsoidal particle as the radius of a volume-equivalent sphere r_v which can be derived as $2r_v = \sqrt[3]{hwl}$, where $h < w < l$ are height, width and length of the ellipsoid, respectively. Accordingly, we define the ellipsoidal size parameter x_v as in Equation A1 but using r_v instead of r :

$$x_v = \frac{2\pi r_v}{\lambda}. \quad (\text{B1})$$

Using the volume-equivalent radius as the ellipsoidal size allows retaining the simple relation between dust mass and number concentration for spheres of Equation A3. Introducing then the projected area (or geometric cross section) of a volume-equivalent sphere, $C_{\text{gv}}(r_v) = \pi r_v^2$, allows writing an expression for the volume-equivalent mean projected area G_v formally identical to Equation A4:

$$G_v = \int \pi r_v^2 f_N(r_v) dr_v, \quad (\text{B2})$$

and thus a definition of the volume-equivalent effective radius r_{ev} consistent with Equation A8:

$$r_{\text{ev}} = \frac{\int r_v \pi r_v^2 f_N(r_v) dr_v}{\int \pi r_v^2 f_N(r_v) dr_v}. \quad (\text{B3})$$

704 However, to derive an equation for the extinction optical depth of ellipsoidal particles
 705 that is formally identical to Equation A6, a further step is required. The complexity arises
 706 because both the extinction cross section and the projected area of an ellipsoid in gen-
 707 eral depend upon its two axis ratios along with its orientation and volume-equivalent ra-
 708 dius.

As a standard definition, the orientation-averaged extinction efficiency of a single ellipsoid is given by its extinction cross section normalized by its orientation-averaged projected area, the latter by definition equal to the projected area of a surface-equivalent sphere $C_{\text{gc}}(r_c) = \pi r_c^2$ (Gasteiger & Wiegner, 2018):

$$Q_{\text{ec}}(m, x_v, \epsilon_1, \epsilon_h) = \frac{C_e(m, x_v, \epsilon_1, \epsilon_h)}{C_{\text{gc}}(r_c)}, \quad (\text{B4})$$

where $\epsilon_1 = l/w$ and $\epsilon_h = h/w$ are the LWR and HWR, respectively, of the ellipsoid. An alternative ellipsoidal extinction efficiency can be defined by normalizing the extinction cross section by the volume-equivalent projected area:

$$Q_{\text{ev}}(m, x_v, \epsilon_1, \epsilon_h) = \frac{C_e(m, x_v, \epsilon_1, \epsilon_h)}{C_{\text{gv}}(r_v)}. \quad (\text{B5})$$

These two definitions of ellipsoidal extinction efficiency are both available in MengDB and used in the literature. For example, while the definition of Equation B4 is used by Bi et al. (2009), the volume-equivalent normalization of Equation B5 is consistent with the extinction efficiency for ellipsoids used by Kok et al. (2017). Comparing Equations B4 and B5, where the extinction cross section must be the same, leads to

$$Q_{\text{ev}}(m, x_v, \epsilon_1, \epsilon_h) = \Phi(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_h) Q_{\text{ec}}(m, x_v, \epsilon_1, \epsilon_h) \quad (\text{B6})$$

where we introduce the geometric ratio

$$\Phi(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_h) = \frac{C_{\text{gc}}(r_c)}{C_{\text{gv}}(r_v)} \quad (\text{B7})$$

709 as the ratio of the surface-equivalent to volume-equivalent projected areas of the ellip-
 710 soid. It can be calculated that the geometric ratio depends only upon the two indepen-
 711 dent axis ratios of the randomly oriented ellipsoid. Moreover, while for a perfect sphere,
 712 the geometric ratio equals one, it increases with increasing deviation from spherical shape
 713 (Gasteiger & Wiegner, 2018), meaning that spheres exhibit the minimal projected area

714 for a given volume. Based upon Equation B6, this implies that the volume-equivalent
 715 extinction efficiency of an ellipsoid (Equation B5) is always larger than the surface-equivalent
 716 extinction efficiency (Equation B4). Therefore, when comparing extinction efficiencies
 717 of spheres and ellipsoids it is important to clarify which definition is used for the latter,
 718 because the volume-equivalent extinction efficiency also includes the effect of the geo-
 719 metric ratio whereas the surface-equivalent extinction efficiency does not.

Using the volume-equivalent extinction efficiency of Equation B5, along with the
 volume-equivalent mean projected area G_v (Equation B2) and volume-equivalent effec-
 tive radius r_{ev} (Equation B3), allows writing a generalized equation for the extinction
 optical depth of ellipsoids that is formally identical to Equation A6:

$$\tau_\lambda = \frac{3 \langle Q_{ev} \rangle}{4\rho r_{ev}} M \Delta z, \quad (\text{B8})$$

where $\langle Q_{ev} \rangle$ is the generalized volume-equivalent projected-area-weighted mean ex-
 tinction efficiency:

$$\langle Q_{ev} \rangle = \frac{\iiint Q_{ev}(m, x_v, \epsilon_1, \epsilon_h) \pi r_v^2 g_N(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_h) f_N(r_v) d\epsilon_1 d\epsilon_h dr_v}{\int \pi r_v^2 f_N(r_v) dr_v}, \quad (\text{B9})$$

720 where $g_N(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_h)$ is the normalized ellipsoidal weighting function that allows averaging
 721 $Q_{ev}(m, x_v, \epsilon_1, \epsilon_h)$ over all the available axis ratios for a given volume-equivalent radius.

722 B2 Methods for size interpolation

723 In MengDB, the size parameter of the ellipsoids is defined based upon their ma-
 724 jor axis (i.e., length: $x_1^* = 2\pi l/\lambda$, where ‘*’ indicates that these are the values tabulated
 725 in MengDB), and spans a grid of one-hundred discrete values ranging from 0.025 to 1000
 726 with constant logarithmic step. The database also provides the corresponding shape-dependent
 727 sets of volume-equivalent size parameters x_v^* that are always smaller than x_1^* by defini-
 728 tion (Meng et al., 2010a). Since we take the volume-equivalent radius as the ellipsoidal
 729 size descriptor (Appendix B1), we perform spline interpolation to map the monodisperse
 730 ellipsoidal optical properties from the x_v^* sets of MengDB onto our grid of prescribed x_v ,
 731 which is the same set of size parameters used for spherical dust (Appendix A2). We cal-
 732 culate that the x_v^* ranges cover our eight size bins for all our prescribed SW wavelengths
 733 across all ellipsoidal shapes available in MengDB.

734 B3 Methods for shape averaging

735 Ellipsoids in MengDB are defined for 21 pairs of distinct aspect ratios defined by
 736 $\alpha_w = w/h = 1.20, 1.50, 1.80, 2.10, 2.40$ and 2.70 combined with $\alpha_1 = l/h = 1.50,$
 737 $1.80, 2.10, 2.40, 2.70, 3.30$, while $\alpha_1 > \alpha_w$. In terms of the MengDB aspect ratios, our
 738 axis ratios (LWR and HWR, respectively) can be written as $\epsilon_1 = l/w = \alpha_1/\alpha_w$ and
 739 $\epsilon_h = h/w = 1/\alpha_w$, with $\epsilon_1 > 1$ and $0 < \epsilon_h < 1$. Following Huang et al. (2023), we
 740 prescribe the probability of each ellipsoidal shape according to empirical log-normal dis-
 741 tributions of LWR (f_l , for its deviation from unity) and HWR (f_h):

$$f_l(\epsilon_1 - 1) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}(\epsilon_1 - 1)\sigma_l} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\ln(\epsilon_1 - 1) - \ln(\bar{\epsilon}_l - 1)}{\sigma_l} \right)^2 \right],$$

$$f_h(\epsilon_h) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\epsilon_h\sigma_h} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\ln(\epsilon_h) - \ln(\bar{\epsilon}_h)}{\sigma_h} \right)^2 \right], \quad (\text{B10})$$

742 which were used by Huang et al. (2020) to fit dozens of in-situ worldwide shape mea-
 743 surement sets including hundreds of thousands of collected dust particles. Huang et al.
 744 (2020) reported moderate regional differences of both the LWR and HWR distributions

745 (although with large uncertainty due to limited samples from some areas) along with a
 746 low sensitivity to particle size. We neglect regional variations in the distribution param-
 747 eters choosing the global medians and geometric standard deviations from Huang et al.
 748 (2020): $\bar{\epsilon}_1 = 1.70 \pm 0.03$ and $\sigma_1 = 0.70 \pm 0.02$ for LWR; $\bar{\epsilon}_h = 0.40 \pm 0.07$ and $\sigma_h =$
 749 0.73 ± 0.09 for HWR. (In this study, we do not account for the uncertainty of the dis-
 750 tribution parameters.)

The two log-normal distributions f_1 and f_h are normalized for $\epsilon_1 > 1$ and $\epsilon_h > 0$, respectively. Assuming that the two axis ratios are independent (Huang et al., 2020), we define the joint probability of a generic ellipsoid as

$$P(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_h) = f_1(\epsilon_1 - 1)f_h(\epsilon_h)\Delta\epsilon_1\Delta\epsilon_h, \quad (\text{B11})$$

where $\Delta\epsilon_1$ and $\Delta\epsilon_h$ are suitable axis ratio integration intervals. In our calculation, we define the integration intervals to evenly cover the axis ratios sampled by MengDB and derive the monodisperse ellipsoidal optical properties for a given r_v as the weighted mean of the 21 ellipsoids available in MengDB (as theoretically derived in Equation B9):

$$X(n_g, k_g, x_v) = \sum_{i=1}^{21} W^i X^i(n_g, k_g, x_v), \quad (\text{B12})$$

751 where W^i represents the re-normalized joint probability of Equation B11 for the i^{th} el-
 752 lipsoid in MengDB, and X generally indicates any of the monodisperse properties, which
 753 is already interpolated at our set of prescribed x_v but still defined on the grid of RRI
 754 (n_g) and IRI (k_g) of MengDB.

755 **B4 Methods for refractive index interpolation**

756 As a last step, we apply bilinear interpolation to derive the monodisperse ellipsoidal
 757 optical properties at the CRI values prescribed for spherical dust (Section 2.2) from a
 758 subset of grid CRIs available in MengDB: $n_g = 1.4, 1.5, 1.6$; $k_g = 0.0005, 0.001, 0.005,$
 759 $0.01, 0.02, 0.05$. We finally generate the ellipsoidal look-up table by applying the same
 760 size integration and band averaging that we perform for spherical dust, as described in
 761 Appendix A2.

762 **Conflict of Interest Statement**

763 The authors declare no conflicts of interest relevant to this study.

764 **Open Research Section**

765 The analysis package for generating the figures of this work, including the analy-
 766 sis scripts, the model outputs of the two shape experiments and other required input data,
 767 are available at Zenodo (Obiso et al., 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111861>),
 768 together with the source code of ModelE2.1 used in this work and the necessary model
 769 input data.

770 The Lorenz-Mie FORTRAN program based on Mishchenko et al. (2002), used in
 771 this work to calculate the optical look-up tables of spherical dust, is publicly available
 772 at <https://www.giss.nasa.gov/staff/mmishchenko/Lorenz-Mie.html> (Mishchenko,
 773 2005).

774 The database of single-scattering properties based on Meng et al. (2010a), used in
 775 this work to calculate the optical look-up tables of ellipsoidal dust, is publicly available
 776 at Zenodo (Meng et al., 2010b, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4959767>).

777 The AERONET Version 3 Level 1.5 inversion data product can be downloaded from
 778 https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/new_web/download_all_v3_inversions.html (AERONET,
 779 2019).

780 The MISR Level 3 aerosol product (daily data) can be downloaded from [https://
 781 asdc.larc.nasa.gov/project/MISR/MIL3DAEN_004](https://asdc.larc.nasa.gov/project/MISR/MIL3DAEN_004) (MISR, 2025).

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